

Hemp Club

This project has received funding
by the European Union's European
Innovation Council and SMEs
Executive Agency COSME
Programme under grant
agreement No [101037874]

Total budget: EUR 587 972.48 |

Total funding: EUR 462 976.00

Competent and Connected
Clusters Unfold the Hemp
Industry Potential for the
European Bioeconomy

What we do

The HempClub project brings together **7 clusters and association** operating in the bioeconomy, advanced manufacturing and hemp production sectors to create **interconnected and interregional supply chains** between operators in primary production, agri-food processing and green chemistry by strengthening industrial symbiosis and sustainable and renewable business models in the **hemp sector**.

- ❖ Improve the **management skills** of cluster managers.
- ❖ Strengthen **cluster excellence capacity** by improving the portfolio of business support services.
- ❖ **Facilitate B2B and C2C collaborative activities** to strengthen interregional strategies for the bioeconomy
- ❖ Enhance **collaboration** and **networking** activities between European organisations.
- ❖ Promote **internationalisation, technology** and **knowledge transfer** through the activation of new opportunities for growth and capacity of excellence for clusters and their members.

Why hemp?

With its **unique chemical properties, environmental benefits, high yield** and **wide range of applications**, hemp is a valuable crop for the bioeconomy, contributing to achieving climate neutrality, although still representing a niche crop in Europe.

Project mission

Encourage interregional
Investments based on the
Smart Specialization Strategy

Contribute to the
achievements of **Green
Deal** and **SDGs**

Support **urban-rural symbiosis**
and **environmental protection**

Supporting the
ClusterXchange
scheme's implementation

Enhance the **industrial
potential** of hemp through the
creation of new cross-sector
value chains

Enhance European
cooperation networks in
**agriculture, advanced
manufacturing** and
bioeconomy fields

Project consortium

Project structure

The **HempCluB** project's structure consists of **6 Work Packages** as indicated below.

WP No.	Work Package Name
1	Cluster management and skills building
2	Portfolio of bioeconomy-added-value services for cluster members
3	Joint collaboration and networking across the hemp value chain
4	ClusterXchange visits for mutual learning and bioeconomy growth
5	Outreach and awareness-raising
6	Project management

Project duration (months): 24 – From 1st February 2022

Coordinating organization: Lombardy Green Chemistry Association (IT)

Project structure

ClusterXChange

- ❖ ClusterXchange is a new pilot scheme to support **short-term exchanges** to better connect Europe's industrial ecosystems. It facilitates transnational cooperation, peer learning, networking and innovation uptake between actors of different industrial clusters.
- ❖ The project will carry out at least **80 short term exchanges** involving SMEs, scale supports organizations, training providers, public authorities and big companies involved or interested in the **hemp sector** and belonging to a COSME participating country.
- ❖ Exchanges will include several activities such as **on-the-job-training** for visiting participants, **sharing of information and experience** between visiting organisation and host organisation, **enhancing market access** and **identification of potential partners** for new cluster organisations and other scaling-up support scaling-up support organisations, **supporting the networking** between clusters.
- ❖ Most of these exchanges will have a duration of **five working days** with a distance between the two involved organisations more than 200 kilometres. A lump sum will be provided to support accommodation and living costs during the exchange.

Standortagentur

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